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Structural Design and Material Selection for a Heat Recovery Steam Generator Main High Pressure Steam Pipe

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Abstract

This study presents the structural design and material selection process for the main high-pressure (HP) steam pipe of a Heat Recovery Steam Generator (HRSG), operating under severe thermal and mechanical conditions. The component, exposed to 610 °C and 145 bar for 200,000 hours, was analyzed in compliance with EN 12952 and EN 10216-2 standards. Two candidate materials, P91 (X10CrMoVNb9-1) and P92 (X10CrWMoVNb9-2) steels, were evaluated in terms of mechanical and thermal properties, allowable stresses, oxidation behavior, and long-term creep and fatigue resistance. The minimum wall thickness and maximum allowable temperature ramp rates were determined according to the relevant standards. Creep, thermal fatigue, and oxidation damages were quantified to assess component lifetime and safety. Results indicate that, under nominal design conditions, both materials fail to meet ASME III safety criteria due to oxidation-driven wall thinning and combined creep-fatigue effects. Alternative configurations with increased thickness and planned component replacements were therefore proposed. A techno-economic analysis showed that the configuration using P92 steel with a 60 mm wall thickness and one mid-life replacement (P92-B) represents the optimal solution, balancing cost, reliability, and durability.

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1. Identification of the reference component, description of its typical working conditions

1.1. Component application

The main high-pressure steam pipe of a Heat Recovery Steam Generator (HRSG) is a critical component that transports superheated steam from the boiler section to the turbine inlet. It is typically located within the steam drum and superheater assembly and must withstand high temperatures (up to 600–650 °C) and pressures (up to 170 bar or more). This pipe forms part of the high-pressure steam cycle, connecting the energy generated in the HRSG to the steam turbine for electricity production. Due to its role in conveying high-energy steam under cyclic thermal and mechanical loads, the pipe's design requires careful structural analysis, material selection, and adherence to pressure equipment standards, such as EN 12952, to ensure safe and reliable operation.

HRSG main high pressure steam pipe

1.2. Manufacturing technology

The Mannesmann process is a method for producing seamless steel pipes from solid cylindrical billets. In this process, a heated billet is first rotated and pressed between two diagonal rollers, creating a cavity at its center due to the compressive and tensile stresses — a phenomenon known as the *Mannesmann effect*. The pierced billet is then elongated and further processed through lamination, rolling, and stretching operations to achieve the required diameter, wall thickness, and length, while also refining the surface finish. This method produces pipes with high strength, dimensional uniformity, and no weld seams, making them ideal for high-pressure or high-temperature applications, such as in oil, gas, and power industries, including high-pressure steam pipes in HRSGs. The pierced billet is then elongated and further processed through lamination, rolling, and stretching operations to

achieve the required diameter, wall thickness, and length, while also refining the surface finish. This method produces pipes with high strength, dimensional uniformity, and no weld seams, making them ideal for high-pressure or high-temperature applications, such as in oil, gas, and power industries, including high-pressure steam pipes in HRSGs.

Mannesmann process

1.3. Damage mechanism

High-temperature components, such as steam pipes in power plants, can be damaged in several ways.

- **Creep** is permanent deformation that occurs under constant stress at elevated temperatures, gradually reducing the material's load-bearing capacity.
- **Thermal fatigue** arises from repeated temperature fluctuations, causing cyclic expansion and contraction that initiate cracks over time.
- **Mechanical fatigue** results from cyclic mechanical loading, producing cracks that can propagate and lead to failure.
- **Oxidation** is the chemical degradation of the material surface due to reaction with oxygen at high temperatures, forming scales that can reduce cross-sectional area and accelerate crack initiation.

These mechanisms often act simultaneously, necessitating careful material selection and structural design to ensure reliable operation.

A typical power plant pipe creep failure, progression from cracking to rupture (Ali 2013)

Fatigue damage (Kim et al. 2009)

Oxidative damage

1.4. Materials composition

P91 is a chromium-molybdenum steel alloy with small additions of vanadium and niobium, commonly used for high-temperature, high-pressure applications due to its good creep strength. P92 is

an improved version of P91, obtained by reducing molybdenum quantity and adding tungsten and boron, which enhances creep resistance and high-temperature stability.

Acciaio T91-P91-X10CrMoVNb9-1:

Composizione chimica secondo ASTM A213 and A335:

	C	Mn	Si	P	S	Cr	Mo	V	W	Nb	B	N	Al	Ni
T91-P91	0.07 0.14	0.30 0.60	0.20 0.50	max 0.020	max 0.010	8.0 9.5	0.85 1.05	0.18 0.25	-	0.06 0.10	-	0.03 0.07	max 0.04	max 0.04

-Mo
+W
+B

Acciaio T92-P92-X10CrWMoVNb9-2:

Composizione chimica secondo ASTM A213 and A335:

	C	Mn	Si	P	S	Cr	Mo	V	W	Nb	B	N	Al	Ni
T92-P92	0.07 0.13	0.30 0.60	max 0.50	max 0.020	max 0.010	8.5 9.5	0.30 0.60	0.15 0.25	1.50 2.00	0.04 0.09	0.0010 0.0060	0.03 0.07	max 0.04	max 0.04

Chemical composition of P91 and P92

1.5. Physical properties at different temperatures

The two materials exhibit similar physical properties, as reported in the literature and technical articles. However, the quality and reliability of the data vary significantly between materials: data for well-studied, widely known materials tend to be more accurate, while information on less common materials is more limited or uncertain.

Young's modulus of P91, P92 and reference normative 12952

Linear expansion coefficient of P91, P92 and reference normative 12952

Specific heat of P91, P92 and reference normative 12952

1.6. Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties are reported in the table below:

Steel	R_m [Mpa]	$R_{0,2}$ [Mpa]	Hardness [HV ₁₀]	R_z (100,000 h / 600 °C)
P91	630 - 830	≥ 450	≤ 265	98
P92	620 - 850	≥ 440	≤ 265	132

Where:

- R_m is the tensile strength (also called ultimate tensile strength) of a material, expressed in megapascals (MPa). It is the maximum stress a material can withstand while being stretched or pulled before it breaks.
- $R_{0,2}$ is the yield strength at 0.2% offset, expressed in MPa. It represents the stress at which a material begins to deform plastically (permanent deformation). Since many materials, especially metals, do not have a perfectly sharp yield point, the 0.2% offset method is used: a line is drawn parallel to the elastic portion of the stress–strain curve, offset by 0.2% strain, and its intersection with the curve defines $R_{0,2}$. Below $R_{0,2}$, the material will return to its original shape if the load is removed; above $R_{0,2}$, permanent deformation occurs.
- **Hardness [HV10]** refers to the Vickers hardness measured with a 10 kgf (kilogram-force) test load. Vickers hardness (HV) quantifies a material's resistance to impact.

- **R_z(100,000 h / 600 °C)** is the maximum stress the material can sustain at 600 °C for 100,000 hours before failure due to creep. P92 steel has a better resistance to creep thanks to the higher quantities of molybdenum (Mo), Vanadium (V), Nitrogen (N), Niobium (Nb), Tungsten (W).

Strength-deformation curve

1.7. Thermal treatment

The steels analyzed undergo two main heat treatments, carried out in sequence:

- Normalizing (1040–1090 °C)
- Tempering (730–780 °C)

During normalizing, the steel is heated above the transformation temperature and then air-cooled. In P91 and P92 steels, this step creates a martensitic microstructure.

The subsequent tempering treatment at 730–780 °C reduces internal stresses and refines the microstructure, resulting in a tempered martensite with finely dispersed carbides and nitrides. This combination of treatments provides the steels with their characteristic strength and creep resistance at elevated temperatures.

Tempering + Normalizing process

2. Definition of the design characteristics of the material

2.1. Operating conditions

The operating conditions of the designed component are defined in the table below:

Description	External diameter [mm]	Internal diameter [mm]	Total operating time [h]	Operating time between two service interruptions [h]	Operating pressure P _o [bar]	Operating temperature T _o [°C]	Test pressure P _s [bar]	Test temperature T _s [°C]
Heat Recovery Steam Generator Main High Pressure Steam Pipe	355.6	-	25 years (200,000 h)	144 (6 days/week with 1 day stop)	145	610	150	620

2.2. Allowable stresses

For the calculation of the permissible stresses at different temperatures, reference was made to the EN 12952 - 3 standard. For rolled or forged steels the standard suggests this relationship:

$$f = \min \left\{ \frac{R_{m20}}{2,4}; \frac{R_{eHtc}}{1,5} \text{ and/or } \frac{R_{p0,2tc}}{1,5}; \frac{R_{mTtc}}{1,25} \right\}$$

The data used for the following analysis have been defined with reference to EN 10216-2, concerning the mechanical properties of seamless pressure pipes, and from interpolation of experimental data in different conditions.

The allowable stress for the two steels are reported in the graphs below:

Sollecitazioni ammissibili (T)
X10CrMoVNb9-1

Allowable stresses for P91 steel

Sollecitazioni ammissibili (T)
X10CrWMoVNb9-2

Allowable stresses for P92 steel

The overlap of the allowable stress curves at different temperatures highlights a wider range of possible applications for the steel X10CrWMoVNb9-2, especially at high temperatures where the difference between the two materials becomes more pronounced.

At the design temperature (610°C) and at the design operating time (200,000h) , the allowable stresses for the two materials are:

- $f_{P91} (610^{\circ}\text{C}, 200,000 \text{ h}) = 42 \text{ MPa}$
- $f_{P92} (610^{\circ}\text{C}, 200,000 \text{ h}) = 50,7 \text{ MPa}$

2.3. Economic comparison

The average cost of the two steels is:

- X10CrMoVNb9-1 \Rightarrow 6500 \$/ton
- X10CrWMoVNb9-2 \Rightarrow 7200 \$/ton

It is useful for the analysis to relate the cost with the allowable stresses, as in the graphs below:

Cost/allowable stresses at different temperatures

Cost/allowable stresses at high temperatures

At the design temperature (610°C) and at the design operating time (200,000h), the cost related to the allowable stresses for the two materials are:

- $Cost_{p91} (610^{\circ}C, 200,000 h) = 142.11 \text{ \$/MPa}$
- $Cost_{p92} (610^{\circ}C, 200,000 h) = 154,76 \text{ \$/MPa}$

3. Definition of the geometry and ramp rate of the component

3.1. Calculation of the minimum thickness according to EN 12952-3 (Chapter 7)

The calculation for the minimum thickness of the pipe is given by the standard EN12952-3, in the chapter 7 as follows:

$$e_{cs} = \frac{p_c d_{os}}{(2f_s - p_c)v + 2p_c}$$

Where:

- $p_c = 150 \text{ MPa}$ is the design pressure
- $d_{os} = 355,6 \text{ mm}$ is the external diameter
- $v = 1$ is the opening efficiency and it is a set value
- f_s is the allowable stress and it is different for the two materials, as in chapter 2.2:
 - $f_{s(P91),T=610^\circ C} = 42 \text{ MPa}$
 - $f_{s(P92),T=610^\circ C} = 50.7 \text{ MPa}$

Consequently the minimum thicknesses for the two materials are:

- $e_{cs(P91)} = 53.88 \text{ mm}$
- $e_{cs(P92)} = 45.848 \text{ mm}$

The reference standard EN12952-3 takes also into account the tolerances on the outer diameter and wall thickness parameters: “The minimum thickness to be installed (e_s), minus the negative tolerance, must be greater than the previously calculated thickness. The thickness actually installed will be the first commercially available value greater than e_s .”

Table 7 — Tolerances on outside diameter and wall thickness

Outside Diameter D mm	Tolerances on D	Tolerances on T for a T/D ratio			
		$\leq 0,025$	$> 0,025$ $\leq 0,050$	$> 0,050$ $\leq 0,10$	$> 0,10$
$D \leq 219,1$	$\pm 1\%$ or $\pm 0,5 \text{ mm}$	$\pm 12,5\%$ or $\pm 0,4 \text{ mm}$ whichever is the greater			
$D > 219,1$	whichever is the greater	$\pm 20\%$	$\pm 15\%$	$\pm 12,5\%$	$\pm 10\%$
<small>^a For outside diameters $D \geq 355,6 \text{ mm}$ it is permitted to exceed the upper wall thickness locally by a further 5% of the wall thickness T.</small>					

Considering the 10% tolerances defined by the standard, the calculated minimal thicknesses are:

- $e_{s(P91)} > 59.87 \text{ mm}$
- $e_{s(P92)} > 50.94 \text{ mm}$

To find the real component thickness that needs to be installed it is necessary to consider the first commercially available value greater than e_{ss} , as stated by the standard. These values are indicated by the standard EN10216-2 Table 6

- $e_{(P91)} = 60 \text{ mm}$
- $e_{(P92)} = 55 \text{ mm}$

3.2. Calculation of the maximum allowable temperature ramp rate according to EN12952-3

In EN 12952-3, the ramp rate (that is, the rate of temperature change during heating or cooling) is defined as a function of the component's geometry, particularly its wall thickness and openings. This is because geometry directly influences how thermal stresses develop inside the material.

Thick-walled components heat up more slowly at the core, creating significant temperature differences between the surface and the interior, which can lead to high thermal stresses. In contrast, thin walls heat more uniformly and experience lower stress levels for the same temperature change.

Annex D of EN 12952-3 provides a simplified approach to determine the allowable ramp rate, relating it to both wall thickness and the number of temperature cycles a component is expected to endure. In essence, the thicker the wall, the slower the temperature should be allowed to change, to avoid excessive thermal stress and fatigue damage.

The standard DIN EN 12952-3 chapter 5.5 defines the procedure for the calculation of the maximum ramp rate as follows:

5.5 Cyclic loading

Boiler components are deemed to be exposed to cyclic loading if the boiler is designed for more than 500 cold start-ups. Where cylindrical or spherical pressure parts with openings are subject to cyclic loading, the following calculation for the allowable temperature change rate v_t shall be carried out:

$$v_t = \left(X - p_o \left(\frac{\alpha_m \times d_m}{n_s \times e_{ms}} - 0,5 \right) \right) \frac{Z}{e_{ms}^2} \quad (5.5-1)$$

where

v_t allowable rate of temperature change in K/s;

p_o is the maximum operating pressure;

d_m is the mean diameter of the shell;

e_{ms} is the minimum wall thickness;

$n_s = 2$ for cylindrical shells or

$n_s = 4$ for spherical shells;

$\alpha_m = 4$ or if there is any doubt that this value is conservative, the exact value α_m for cylindrical shells taken from Figure 13.4-5 or α_{sp} for spherical shells, taken from Figure 13.4-7 shall be used;

$X = 550 \text{ N/mm}^2$;

$Z = 2 \text{ K mm}^4/(\text{Ns})$ for ferritic steels, or

$Z = 1 \text{ K mm}^4/(\text{Ns})$ for austenitic and martensitic steels, or

$$Z = - \frac{0,5 D_{th}}{\gamma_{cyl/sp} \alpha_t \beta_t E / (1 - \nu)} \quad (5.5-2)$$

where exact values D_{th} , β_t , E , ν may be taken from Annex D, $\gamma_{cyl/sp}$ from Figures 13.4-6 or 13.4-9 and α_t from Figure 13.4-8.

If the result of this calculation is smaller than the required temperature transient at start-up, or if it is negative, then 13.4 shall apply.

$$u_0 = \frac{d_o}{d_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_{cyl} = \frac{(u_0^2 - 1)(3u_0^2 - 1) - 4u_0^4 \ln u_0}{8(u_0^2 - 1)(u_0 - 1)^2}$$

Figure 13.4-6 — Shape factor γ_{cyl} for cylindrical shells

$$\alpha_1 = \left\{ \left[2 - \frac{h + 2700}{h + 1700} z + \frac{h}{h + 1700} (\exp(-7z) - 1) \right]^2 + 0,81z^2 \right\}^{1/2} \quad \text{and } z = d_{mb}/d_{ms}$$

$$\text{heat-transfer coefficient: } h = \left. \begin{array}{l} 1000 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K} \text{ for steam} \\ 3000 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ for water} \end{array} \right\}$$

Key
 1 water
 2 steam

Figure 13.4-8 — Stress concentration factor due to thermal stress α_1 for cylindrical and spherical shells

The data required from the standard are calculated and presented in the following tables:

material properties:			P91		P92	
tensile strength at room temperature	Rm	N/mm ²	630		620	
yield strength at t*	Re(t*)	N/mm ²	312		352	
coefficient of linear thermal expansion at t*	betaL	1/K	1,218E-05		1,21E-05	
modules of elasticity at t*	E	N/mm ²	1,84E+05		1,81E+05	
thermal diffusivity at t*	Dth	mm ² /s	5,65389		5,36E+00	
Poisson's ratio	ny		0,3		0,3	
component dimensions:						
outside diameter of the drum	do	mm	355,6		355,6	
mean wall thickness of the drum	ems	mm	60		55	
mean diameter of the drum	dms	mm	295,6		300,6	
outside diameter of the branch	dob	mm	51	150	51	150
mean wall thickness of the branch	emb	mm	12	40	12	40
mean diameter of the branch	dmb	mm	39	110	39	110

cycling data:			
cycle number:			1
cycle type:			cold start
calculation pressure	pc	N/mm ²	15
calculation temperature	tc	°C	620
operating pressure	po	N/mm ²	15
min. cyclic pressure	pmin	N/mm ²	0
max. cyclic pressure	pmax	N/mm ²	15
min. cyclic temperature	tmin	°C	20
max. cyclic temperature	tmax	°C	620
reference temperature	t*	°C	470

The ramp rate is considered for 2,000 ON/OFF cycles as indicated by the standard:

13.1.2 Fatigue loading

The numbers and types of transient events, such as start-ups and load changes, to be experienced by the boiler during its design life shall be specified by the purchaser. If they are not specified, 2000 cold start-ups shall be assumed, with increased fatigue damage margins as defined in 13.1.4.

With all the information presented above, the ramp rates are calculated for the two materials and for the two openings present in the component.

	P1 (th=60mm)		P2 (th=55mm)	
	Big opening	Small opening	Big opening	Small opening
Max ramp rate (2,000 cycles) [K/min]	13,36	10,55	16,72	12,64

As expected, the ramp rate for the P92 steel is higher because the thickness is smaller. As explained at the beginning of this paragraph.

Is it also interesting to notice that the maximum allowable ramp rate is smaller for the small openings. This is directly related to a higher *stress concentration factor due to thermal stress* (α_s) for the small openings. Accordingly to figure 13.4-8 from Annex D of EN 12952-3:

	P1 (th=60mm)		P2 (th=55mm)	
	Big opening	Small opening	Big opening	Small opening
stress concentration factor due to thermal stress (α_s)	1.19	1.60	1.20	1.61

This can be explained by the fact that small openings or small sections in a pressure component act as stress concentrators. When the temperature changes rapidly, these areas can't expand or contract as freely as the surrounding material. The restriction creates localized thermal stresses that can be much higher than in larger, more open sections.

So, if the opening is small, even a moderate temperature change can cause significant stress in that region. To prevent this, the allowable ramp rate is reduced for small openings, giving the material more time to expand lowering the risk of local damage.

4. Assessment of the material conditions in the operating component

4.1. Creep damage calculation

Creep damage represents the progressive and irreversible degradation of a material subjected to high temperature and constant stress over time. It occurs due to long-term exposure that causes time-dependent plastic deformation and eventually rupture. To quantify creep damage it is necessary to compare the time a component has been exposed to a given stress and temperature with the material's expected rupture time under those same conditions. The ratio of these two times represents the fraction of life consumed, and by summing these fractions over all operating conditions the total creep damage is obtained.

From the *creep rupture strength values* given in EN10216-2 Annex A, it is possible to find the theoretical rupture strength as a function of the operating temperature and operating stress ($R_{m,T,tc}$) and following the indications in EN12952-4 Annex A it is possible to find the *time to reach the theoretical rupture by creep* (T_{al}). Consequently it is defined the formula to calculate the creep damage.

Annex A (informative)

Calculation of in-service creep damage

A.1 General

This annex describes a procedure for calculating the creep damage of a boiler and its major components during operation. It is based on measured values of pressure and temperature, from which the actual primary stress and the expected lifetime at these conditions may be determined.

Design lifetime is not necessarily identical with the operating lifetime. It is therefore necessary to make projections at various stages throughout the operating lifetime of the boiler to determine its expected lifetime.

A.2 Symbols and abbreviations

In addition to the symbols given in EN 12952-1:2001, Table 4-1, the symbols given in Table A.1 apply.

Table A.1 — Symbols

Symbol	Description	Unit
f_{op}	Membrane stress at operating conditions	N/mm ²
T_{op}	Operated time at operating conditions	h
T_{th}	Time to reach the theoretical rupture by creep	h
D_c	Creep damage	—

A.3 Calculation of in-service lifetime and creep damage

A.3.1 General

The calculation of the usage factor due to creep is a method that retrospectively takes into consideration the previous modes of operation. It is carried out for highly loaded components on the basis of the measured operating temperatures and gauge pressures.

In order to limit the number of the required calculations and to more clearly present the results, the pressure and temperature range over which the component has been operated, shall be broken down into increments.

The membrane stress f_{op} at the highest loaded point in the component shall be obtained by transposing the design formula using the mean pressure of each pressure increment. If the operating pressure is not measured continuously during operation the separation into increments is not valid and under such circumstances the operating pressure for 100 % load may be used, thus resulting in more conservative predictions. If available, the measured minimum wall thickness may be used. If this was not measured, the guaranteed minimum wall thickness of the material as delivered shall be used.

The theoretical lifetime T_{th} shall be calculated for each rating temperature/pressure. According to Figure A.1, T_{th} is obtained at the intersection of the stress line f_{op} and the lower limit curve of the scatter band of the creep rupture strength ($= 0,8 R_{m,T,c}$) at the mean temperature of each temperature increment.

The respective portion of the creep damage $\Delta D_{c,k}$ for each incremental temperature/pressure is obtained by the ratio of the operating time T_{op} for this increment divided by the theoretical lifetime T_{th} for the same increment.

6

Key
a) lg (R_m)
b) lg (T), h

Figure A.1 — Diagram for the determination of T_{al}

The operating times in the temperature/pressure increment shall be summarized, taking into account the temperature allowances for measuring uncertainties and for temperature asymmetries in due consideration at this classification.

The usage portion for each increment is given by

$$\Delta D_{cl,k} = \frac{T_{op}}{T_{al}} \quad (A.1)$$

The creep damage D_c during the evaluated period shall be obtained from the linear damage rule by summing up the values $\Delta D_{cl,k}$ for all temperature increments and, if any, pressure as follows:

$$D_c = \sum_1 \sum_k \Delta D_{cl,k} \quad (A.2)$$

The creep damage has been calculated for both materials and it is given as a percentage. It represents the fraction of the component's creep life that has been consumed. For example, a creep damage of 40% means that roughly 40% of the material's expected life under the given operating conditions has been used up, while 100% indicates that the component has reached its predicted end-of-life due to creep.

Material	Operative temperature T_0 [°C]	Operative pressure P_0 [MPa]	Total operating time t_{design} [h]	D_{ext} [mm]	D_{int} [mm]	Welding factor [-]	Operating stress f_{op} [MPa]	Effective operating time (T_{al})	Creep damage D_c [%]
P91	610	14.5	200'000	355.6	235.6	1	35.72	5'610'718	3.56
P91 Welding check	610	14.5	200'000	355.6	235.6	0.8		1'574'803	12.7
P92	610	14.5	200'000	355.6	245.6	1	39.62	10'849'374	1.84
P92 Welding check	610	14.5	200'000	355.6	235.6	0.8		3'448'276	5.8

Where:

- $f = \frac{p \cdot d_{is}}{2v \cdot e_{cs}} + \frac{p}{2}$

Creep damage values of 3.56% and 1.84%, means that only a small fraction of the component's creep life has been consumed after 200'000 hours of operation.

4.2. Creep-fatigue damages combination

Thermal fatigue occurs when a material is repeatedly heated and cooled, causing it to expand and contract over and over again. Even without an external load, these temperature changes create alternating stresses that can eventually lead to small cracks, especially in areas with sharp temperature gradients or irregular shapes. Over time, those cracks can grow and weaken the component. This phenomenon is particularly important in high-temperature systems like turbines or boilers, where parts regularly go through heating and cooling cycles.

Thermal fatigue often works hand in hand with creep, since both are influenced by temperature and stress. At high temperatures, the material not only suffers from these stress cycles but also slowly deforms over time due to creep. During the hot periods, creep strain can build up and make fatigue cracks grow faster, while the plastic strain from fatigue can raise local stresses and speed up creep damage. Together, these two effects reinforce each other, leading to earlier failure than if either acted alone.

Thermal fatigue damage is calculated according to EN12952-4 Annex B.

Material	Operative temperature T_0 [°C]	Operative pressure P_0 [MPa]	Welding factor [-]	Creep damage D_c [%]	Thermal fatigue D_f @ 12K/min [%]
P91	610	14.5	1	3.56	95.3
P91 Welding check	610	14.5	0.8	12.7	95.3
P92	610	14.5	1	1.84	59.9
P92 Welding check	610	14.5	0.8	5.8	59.9

The combined effect is evaluated according to the diagram proposed by ASME III, N-47 Code Case. The yellow dots are related to the P91 steel and the light blue dots are related to the P92.

According to ASME III none of these materials are compliant with the designed application, because they both fall out of the safety area delimited by the red lines. The P92 steel could be suitable but due to the welding sections, it can't be used reliably.

4.3. Oxidation

The oxidation is the chemical degradation of the material surface due to reaction with oxygen at high temperatures, forming scales that can reduce cross-sectional area and accelerate crack initiation.

This thickness degradation develops linearly and it is described by the Metal Thinning Rate (MTR).

The MTR is given by experimental data and literature. Considering the operating time of 200'000 hours, the lost thickness can be calculated by multiplying the MTR with the operating time.

Material	MTR [$\mu\text{m}/1000\text{h}$]	Lost thickness due to oxidation e_{lost} [mm]	Thickness after 200'000 hours [mm]	Minimum required thickness as calculated in 3.1 [mm]
P91	60	12	48	59.87
P92	80	16	39	50.94

Consequently the operating stress will increase with time as in the graph below:

Increase of stress over time due to oxidation induced thickness reduction

4.4. Conclusion

Both materials can't be used for the design application because:

- Creep and fatigue combination damages are out of the safety are defined by ASME III as shown in 4.2
- The oxidation will make the thickness smaller than the minimum value defined by EN12952-3 (calculated in 3.1), as shown in 4.3

For these reasons the components must be changed during its operational life. Since the oxidation is the most critical damage mechanism for our case study, the replacements will be planned according to the oxidation damages. Assuming that the pipe must be changed when it reaches the minimum allowable thickness (e_{cs}) defined in Chapter 3.1 and as said in 4.3, the thickness decreases linearly over time according to the MTR, it is possible to calculate after how many hours the component need to be replaced:

Material	Commercial available thickness [mm]	Minimum allowable thickness e_{cs} [mm]	MTR [$\mu\text{m}/1000\text{h}$]	Allowed operating time [hours]	Allowed operating time [days]
P91	60	59.87	60	2233	108.9
P92	55	50.94	80	50725	2472,6

If the component is realized with P91 material, a replacement is necessary after only about 4 months. On the other hand, by choosing the P92 steel, the replacement can occur almost every 7 years.

4.5. Further solutions

In this chapter an alternative solution is analyzed. As already said, since oxidation is the most critical damage mechanism in the given conditions, it makes sense to oversize the thickness of the material to get rid of the oxidation problem with a good margin of safety. Three different solutions for each material will be studied:

4.5.1. Further solutions for P91

The solutions for the P91 steel are described in table below:

Configuration	Number of replacements	Number of components	Operating time of each component [hours]	Chosen commercial thickness [mm]
P91-A	0	1	200'000	80
P91-B	1	2	100'000	70
P91-C	2	3	66'667	65

Since the oxidation is not a problem with this thickness, for these configurations only the other damage mechanisms will be evaluated (Creep and thermal fatigue).

Configuration	Operating time of each component [hours]	N° of ON/OFF cycles	Creep damage D_c [%]	Max Ramp rate [K/min]	Fatigue damage @12 K/min D_f [%]	Suitability
P91-A	0	1500	0,62 %	7,15	354 %	✗
P91-B	1	750	0,80 %	12,40	93 %	✓
P91-C	2	500	0,89 %	17,13	44 %	✓

The combined effect is evaluated according to the diagram proposed by ASME III, N-47 Code Case. The blue dot represents the P91-C configuration while the green dot represents the P91-B

configuration. The P91-A configuration is out of the graph since it causes fatigue damage much greater than 1.

As we can see from the graph below both configuration B and C are inside the safety area defined by the ASME III, N-47 Code Case, furthermore both configurations allow a maximum ramp rate higher than the design ramp rate of 12 K/min. Hence both configurations are safe to use.

4.5.2. Further solutions for P92

The solutions for the P92 steel are described in table below:

Configuration	Number of replacements	Number of components	Operating time of each component [hours]	Chosen commercial thickness [mm]
P92-A	0	1	200'000	70
P92-B	1	2	100'000	60
P92-C	2	4	50'000	55

Since the oxidation is not a problem with this thickness, for these configurations only the other damage mechanisms will be evaluated (Creep and thermal fatigue).

Configuration	Operating time of each component [hours]	N° of ON/OFF cycles	Creep damage D_c [%]	Max Ramp rate [K/min]	Fatigue damage @12 K/min D_f [%]	Suitability
P92-A	0	1500	0,96 %	9,71	168 %	✘
P92-B	1	750	0,99 %	17,42	42 %	✔
P92-C	2	375	0,75 %	28,11	21 %	✔

The combined effect is evaluated according to the diagram proposed by ASME III, N-47 Code Case. The blue dot represents the P92-C configuration while the green dot represents the P92-B configuration. The P92-A configuration is out of the graph since it causes fatigue damage much greater than 1.

As we can see from the graph below both configuration B and C are inside the safety area defined by the ASME III, N-47 Code Case, furthermore both configurations allow a maximum ramp rate higher than the design ramp rate of 12 K/min. Hence both configurations are safe to use.

4.6. Technical-economic analysis

The technical-economic analysis is summarized in the table below:

Configuration	Commercial thickness [mm]	N° of components	Steel density [kg/m ³]	External diameter [mm]	Cross section area [mm ²]	Cost [\$/ton]	Calculated cost [\$/m]	Oxidation resistance	Creep + fatigue resistance	Max ramp rate > 12 K/min
P91-A	80	0	7770	355.6	69'266	6500	3498	✓	✗	✗
P91-B	70	1	7770	355.6	62'807	6500	6344	✓	✗	✓
P91-C	65	2	7770	355.6	59'341	6500	8991	✓	✓	✓
P92-A	70	1	7850	355.6	62'807	7200	3550	✓	✗	✗
P92-B	60	2	7850	355.6	55'719	7200	6299	✓	✓	✓
P92-C	55	4	7850	355.6	51'940	7200	11743	✓	✓	✓

The options that can be chosen are the P91-C, P92-B and P92-C because they respect all the safety criteria. The technical-economic analysis leads to choosing among the possible alternatives, which satisfy the specified conditions, the one with the lowest overall costs which is the P92-B option.

References

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